

Interactive Effect of Gender and Two Teaching Strategies On Pre-Service Teachers' Performance in Basic Science in Nigerian Colleges of Education

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Abstract:

The study investigated interactive effect of gender and teaching strategies (Reflective Teaching, Peer Tutoring and Conventional Teaching) on the performance of pre-service teachers in Basic Science. The study adopted pre-test and post-test control group quasi-experimental design. The population of the study consisted of all pre-service teachers studying Basic Science as teaching subject in all the 12 public Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted of 124 pre-service teachers of Basic Science from the three selected Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria through multistage sampling procedure. Pre-service Teachers' Achievement Test in Basic Science (PTATBS) was used for data collection and divided into two sections A and B. The face and content validity of PTATBS was ensured by experts of Basic Science. The method of split-half was used to establish the reliability coefficient 0.81 for PTATBS as administered on 40 pre-service teachers outside the sampled area. The experimental procedure was in three phases. Inferential statistics of two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that the performance of the pre-service teachers exposed to Reflective Teaching, Peer Tutoring and Conventional Teaching was not influenced by their gender. The use of Reflective Teaching and Peer Tutoring instructional strategies should be

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encouraged in teaching pre-service teachers of Basic Science in Colleges of Education to enhance their professional skills since the strategies are not gender biased.

Keywords: Basic Science, Gender, Peer Tutoring, Performance, Pre-service Teachers, Reflective,

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Introduction

The importance of a teacher in any educational setting cannot be overemphasized as they are the pivot on which the system hinges. It is obvious that for Colleges of Education in Nigeria to produce teachers, who possess knowledge and classroom skills that would remain in the teaching profession and influence students' performance positively. College of Education students are expected to acquire adequate knowledge and perform excellently so as to fulfill the main objective of establishing the teacher training school, which is to produce quality and competent teachers for primary and junior secondary schools. Basic Science enables students to develop an understanding of application of scientific knowledge to everyday activities. It helps youngster to excel in the field related to applied science and aids systematic progress in technology.

Gender is one of the variables of interest considered to have great influence on pre-service teachers' performance in Colleges of Education in Nigeria, especially in science subjects. Gender is the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between the feminine and masculine (female and male) population. The importance of examining performance in relation to gender is based primarily on the socio-cultural differences between girls and boys. What has remained the main focus of great concern in the field of science education are the biases and misconceptions about women and science, i.e. science is a male enterprise (Erinosho, 2005). Gender has remained an issue in the front burner of academic discourse. Scholars have become enthusiastic on addressing issues that have continued to create differences among people on the basis of gender which has continued to have adverse consequences on sustainable economic development of the nation (Imam & Dada 2011). Imam and Dada (2011) defined gender as the social roles, responsibilities, and behavior created in our families, societies and culture.

It is not surprising then that the school, being a microcosm of society, consciously or unconsciously perpetuates stereotypical behaviour, and, indeed, teachers within the system exhibit gender bias in the classrooms (Arigbabu & Mji, 2010). For example, it has been reported that teachers, consciously or unconsciously, often mete out differential treatment to boys and girls in their classrooms (Rubble & Martins, 2008). Students, on their part, tend to have formed a stereotypical concept of mathematician and scientists whom they regard as a special group. In such a concept, female students (Mothers of tomorrow) do not see themselves as having the potential to become mathematicians and scientists (Arigbabu & Mji, 2010).

The greater disadvantage and under-representation of females over males in scientific and technologically-related specialties, career and even in leadership positions in Nigeria is a fact that certain factors impinging on gender equality and preference may be responsible for the seeming non-participation of females. However, this does not create any impression of poorer performance. Girls and boys are equally brilliant or equally dull (Duyilemi, 2005). The issue of gender differences needs further examination since a number of studies especially in Nigeria have reported that girls are under-represented in the fields of science and technology at secondary and tertiary institutions level (Kingdom & Cassen, 2007).

It also includes the expectations held about the characteristics, aptitudes and likely behaviors of both men and women. These roles are passed on from generation to generation (United States Aid for Individual Development (USAID), 2005). Topping et al. (2011) view gender as a

social, historical and cultural construct and conditioning, indicating acceptable and preferable forms of behavior and attitudes for both men and women in the society.

Gender can also be viewed as a socially ascribed attribute which differentiates feminine from masculine. Oraifo (2000) opined that sex is based on biological and physical differences between male and female while gender refers to cultural understanding about what constitutes masculinity and femininity in a society. Thus, while sex is biologically defined, gender is socially defined. On another note, Onyebuanyi (2009) stated that “being male or female is a matter of sex but to be masculine or feminine is a matter of gender”. Gender roles are therefore not only different but unequal. Masculinity, according to Onyebuanyi refers to attributes appropriate for males such as being aggressive, athletic, physically active, logical and dominant in social relations with females. The author maintained that femininity refers to attributes and traditionally with appropriate behavior for females such as docility, fragility, emotionality and subordination to males.

According to UNESCO (2003), females constitute more than fifty percent (50%) of the world’s active population and though they make immense contribution to national development, they still face a number of inequitable difficulties that limit their potentials in prompting personal and collective development. A key area of concern in this is that of their participation in science. Gender difference in science, from the views of Myra and David (1991) as cited by Sakiyo (2007) is the intentional or unintentional treatment of females in science in our educational system where boys receive significantly more remediation, criticism and praise than girls. Gender should not be allowed to restrict total development of the potentials of anybody because whatever reason that makes science attractive to males, does the same for females. Ezeliora (2002) submits that women and girls need science education for some reasons. One is that growing population is bringing and increasing pressure on natural resources and the environment. We need to find ways to use the same resources in more different ways. Another is that in this era of technological development, every profession uses the result of science and technology so the women/girls should also be prepared for it. Also, growing demoralization increasingly involves the population in decision-making and to be able to decide, women need to be able to choose.

Women in science came into limelight during the United Nations Decade for Women (1976-1985) which addressed women in science and the challenges confronting women in choosing and performing well in science related occupations (Otuka (2004). The association between gender and the response to Science, Technology and Mathematics (STM) education has been widely studied (Anegbe & Adeoye, 2006). The main focus of their findings is lack of girls opting to study the physical sciences. Studies on gender differences in science achievement, interest and participation are enormous in science education. The finding contradict that of Ezenwosu and Nworgu (2009) in their study titled, Efficacy of Peer Tutoring and Gender on Students’ Achievement in Biology revealed that the influence of gender on student academic achievement in biology was not significant. Contrarily, Obiunu (2008) in his study titled the effects of Reciprocal Peer Tutoring on the enhancement of career decision making process among secondary school adolescents that indicated that sex is not a significant factor, in the career decision-making of adolescent students in the study treatment groups.

It appears that male pre-service Basic Science teachers perform better than their female counterparts (Ibidiran, 2017). Also, equality and difference in the achievement of male and

female pre-service teachers in Basic Science has formed an important focus of research for some years now. The issue of gender disparity in Basic Science performance of pre-service teachers particularly was also clearly detected by Alio and Harbor (2000). It is obvious that the way students learn is as important as what they learn. This is to say that the selection of an adequate usage of an appropriate and most efficient and effective method are very vital to the success of any lesson (Iji, 2007).

Based on the foregoing, this study investigated the interactive effect of gender and two teaching strategies (Reflective Teaching and Peer Tutoring) on pre-service teachers' performance in Basic Science in Nigerian Colleges of Education. Reflective Teaching (RT) is a teaching strategy which involves observing what you do in the classroom, thinking about why you do it, with a view to re-strategize for better performance in the classroom (Adedayo, 2014). It is a process of self-observation and self-evaluation. It is a means of professional development which begins in our classroom. It is paying critical attention to the practical values and theories which inform everyday action, by examining practice reflectively and reflexively (Adedayo, 2014). Peer Tutoring (PT) could be defined as a learning situation where students take turns acting as the tutors and the tutees for instruction or review of academic material (Ogundola, 2017). In this case, students exchange roles during tutoring session, both giving and receiving academic assistance while the teacher supervises rather than participate in the intervention. The goal of Peer Tutoring is to use discussion to enhance students' reading learning, develop self-regulatory and monitoring skills, and achieve overall improvement in motivation (Pulling & Allen, 2014).

The study specifically investigated interactive effect of gender and teaching strategies (Reflective Teaching, Peer Tutoring and Conventional Teaching) on the performance of pre-service teachers in Basic Science. The following hypotheses were formulated:

Ho1: There is no significant interactive effect of gender and teaching strategies (Reflective Teaching and Conventional Teaching) on the performance of pre-service teachers in Basic Science.

Ho2: There is no significant interactive effect of gender and teaching strategies (Peer Tutoring and Conventional Teaching) on the performance of pre-service teachers in Basic Science.

Research Method

The study adopted pre-test and post-test control group quasi-experimental design. The population of the study consisted of all pre-service teachers studying Basic Science as teaching subject in all the 12 public Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted of 124 pre-service teachers of Basic Science from the three selected Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria through multistage sampling procedure. Pre-service Teachers' Achievement Test in Basic Science (PTATBS) was used for data collection and divided into two sections A and B. Section A sought for the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents while Section B consisted of thirty multiple-choice objective test items drawn from the topics taught.

The face and content validity of PTATBS was ensured by experts of Basic Science. Their suggestions, corrections and opinions helped in effecting the necessary modifications. The method of split-half was used to establish the reliability coefficient 0.81 for PTATBS as administered on 40 pre-service teachers outside the sampled area. The experimental

procedure was in three phases namely pre-treatment, treatment and post-treatment phases. Inferential statistics of two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant interactive effect of gender and teaching strategies (Reflective Teaching and Conventional Teaching) on the performance of pre-service teachers in Basic Science.

In testing the hypothesis, post-test mean scores of pre-service teachers exposed to Reflective Teaching and Conventional Teaching were computed and compared for statistical significance using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level based on gender. The result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: 2X2 ANOVA of Performance of Pre-service Teachers Exposed to Reflective Teaching (RT) and Conventional Teaching (CT) in Basic Science by Gender.

Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p
Corrected Model	1388.129	3	462.710	78.923	.000
Gender	.015	1	.015	.003	.960
Group	1239.554	1	1239.554	211.427	.000
Gender * Group	2.443	1	2.443	.417	.521
Error	422.121	72	5.863		
Total	34533.000	76			
Corrected Total	1810.250	75			

p>0.05

Table 1 reveals that the computed F-value (0.417) obtained for the groups with a p value > 0.05 was not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that there is no significant interactive effect of gender and teaching strategies (Reflective Teaching and Conventional Teaching) on the performance of pre-service teachers in Basic Science. Similarly, the effect of gender on the posttest mean scores of pre-service teachers in Basic Science is not significant at 0.05 level ($F_{1,72}=0.003$, $p>0.05$). However, treatment had significant effect on the posttest mean scores of pre-service teachers in Basic Science ($F_{1,72}=211.427$, $p<0.05$).

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant interactive effect of gender and teaching strategies (Peer Tutoring and Conventional Teaching) on the performance of pre-service teachers in Basic Science.

In testing the hypothesis, posttest mean scores of pre-service teachers exposed to Peer Tutoring and Conventional Teaching were computed and compared for statistical significance using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) based on gender. The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: 2 X 2 ANOVA of Performance of Pre-service Teachers Exposed to Peer Tutoring (PT) and Conventional Teaching (CT) in Basic Science by Gender.

Source	SS	df	MS	F	P
Corrected Model	1958.432	3	652.811	113.892	.000
Gender	3.125	1	3.125	.545	.462
Group	1819.528	1	1819.528	317.441	.000
Gender * Group	.006	1	.006	.001	.974
Error	487.208	85	5.732		
Total	45039.000	89			
Corrected Total	2445.640	88			

p>0.05

Table 2 reveals that the computed F-value (0.001) obtained for the groups with a p value > 0.05 was not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that there is no significant interactive effect of gender and teaching strategies (Peer Tutoring and Conventional Teaching) on the performance of pre-service teachers in Basic Science. Similarly, the effect of gender on the posttest mean scores of pre-service teachers in Basic Science is not significant at 0.05 level ($F_{1,85}=0.545$, $p>0.05$). However, treatment had significant effect on the posttest mean scores of pre-service teachers in Basic Science ($F_{1,85}=317.441$, $p<0.05$).

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that there was no significant interactive effect of gender on performance of pre-service teachers exposed to Reflective Teaching, Peer-Tutoring and Conventional teaching strategies in Basic Science. The findings agree with the submission of Ezenwosu and Nworgu (2009) that students' gender has no influence on academic achievement of pre-service teachers in biology. However, the study contradicts Alio and Harbor-Peters (2000) who found gender disparity in performance of pre-service teachers in Basic Science. The findings of this study showed that pre-service teachers' gender has no barrier to their academic performance in Basic Science, but the strategies used by their lecturers to teach them. It therefore implies that effective use of the two strategies (Reflective Teaching and Peer-Tutoring) would enhance better performance of pre-service teachers in Basic Science irrespective of their gender.

Conclusion and Recommendation

It was concluded that the performance of the pre-service teachers exposed to Reflective Teaching, Peer Tutoring and Conventional Teaching was not influenced by their gender. The use of Reflective Teaching and Peer Tutoring instructional strategies should be encouraged in teaching pre-service teachers of Basic Science in Colleges of Education to enhance their professional skills since the strategies are not gender biased.

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